

EXCELLENT VALUES OF TRIBAL CULTURE FAMILY AND ITS EFFECT ON EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A SPECIAL REFERENCE IN PANCHMAHAL DISTRICT GUJARAT

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Abstract

Tribal values are an essential part of the tribe's self-knowledge and identity. As such, they are integral to 'growing up', becoming an independent, responsible and empowered autonomous individual in a tribal society. Such a type of Value is denoted as excellent Value. The excellent values are an integral part of tribes' deep, private self-definition and a driver of their publicly observed behaviour. The tribals are children of nature, and the ecosystem conditions their lifestyle. Tribal peoples have different spheres of life: social, economic, cultural, hereditary, physical, religious, spiritual, moral, biological, political, and cosmic (natural laws). These are also practical and scientific, as applied to Dharma, Artha, Kama, and Moksha. The tribe has a unique identity, cultural lifestyle, and connection to nature that set it apart from others. Tribes have a genetically arranged past. Excellent values by which they spent their whole lives, and a variety of cultures related to tribal people in olden eras, and progress in education in the present era.

Keywords: Excellent Value, Education, Culture, Educational Development

Introduction

India has the largest concentration of tribal people in the world, after Africa. The tribals are children of nature, and the ecosystem conditions their lifestyle. Generally, some tribal people living in mountainous, hilly, and forest regions are considered simpletons and lead a straightforward way of life. Such tribal people are known as "Vanvasis", that is, forest-dwellers. They are the original inhabitants of these areas. "G.W.E. Hunting Ford" defines "A tribe as a group united under a common name in which the members take pride, by a common language, by common territory and by a feeling that all who do not share this name are outsiders, 'enemies' in fact". There is no evidence have found from Gujarat regarding the origin of the various tribes. It has yet to be discovered from where these tribal people came to Gujarat. According to "T.H.E. Sangha", the resemblance that the Indian tool types bear to the African type suggests that the early man in India might have come from Africa. There are references in the Mahabharata and the Bhagavata Purana regarding the tribal population in India. When Lord Rama, Sita and Laxman were going through the forest, Sabari, a Bhilla woman, offered wild fruit to Rama. There are very few regions in the Indian sub-continent with Gujarat's rich prehistoric cultural traditions.

Excellent Value

Our values are essential to our self-knowledge and identity. As such, they are integral to 'growing up', becoming an independent, responsible and empowered autonomous individual. Such a type of Value is denoted as excellent Value. Our excellent values are an integral part of our deep, private self-definition and a driver of our publicly observed behaviour.

- Excellent Values are beliefs. However, they are beliefs tied to emotion, not objective, cold ideas.
- Excellent Values are a motivational construct. They refer to the desirable goals tribal people strive to attain.
- Excellent Values transcend specific actions and situations. They are abstract goals. The abstract nature of values distinguishes them from concepts like norms and attitudes, which usually refer to specific actions, objects, or situations.
- Excellent Values, selecting or evaluating actions, policies, tribal people, and events. That is, values serve as standards or criteria.

- Excellent Values are ordered by their relative importance. Tribal people's values form an ordered system of priorities that characterize individuals. This hierarchical feature of values also distinguishes them from norms and attitudes.

Type of Excellent Value

Schwartz (2005) details the derivations of the ten fundamental values. Each of the ten fundamental values is characterized by describing its central motivational goal:

1. **Self-Direction-** Independent thought and action; choosing, creating, exploring.
2. **Stimulation-** Excitement, novelty, and challenge in life.
3. **Hedonism-** Pleasure and sensuous gratification for oneself.
4. **Achievement-** Tribal people succeed through demonstrating competence according to social standards.
5. **Power-** Social status and prestige, control or dominance over tribal people and resources.
6. **Security-** Safety, harmony, and stability of society, relationships, and self.
7. **Conformity-** Restraint of actions, inclinations, and impulses likely to upset or harm others and violate social expectations or norms.
8. **Tradition-** Respect, commitment, and acceptance of the customs and ideas that traditional culture or religion provides.
9. **Benevolence-** Preserving and enhancing the welfare of those with whom one is in frequent tribal people contact (the 'in-group').
10. **Universalism-** Understanding, appreciation, tolerance, and protection for the welfare of all tribal people and nature.

A History of Tribe in Gujarat

Mainly, tribal groups live in the eastern belt of Gujarat, from Banaskantha to Umargam in Valsad. There are 25 tribal groups in Gujarat. Adivasi is also known as 'Raniparj'. Among the tribals of Gujarat, they are mainly found in the Banaskantha, Sabarkantha, and Aravalli districts in North Gujarat, and in Dahod, Panchmahal, Mahisagar, Vadodara, and Chhota Udaipur in South Gujarat. Adivasis of North Gujarat mainly live in the hilly areas of North Gujarat. The tribes of central Gujarat are located along the mountain and coastal borders. The Aadiwasi culture of Gujarat is found in the tribal districts of Bharuch, Narmada, Surat, Tapi, Navsari, Valsad, Dang, etc. of Gujarat. To a large extent, this tribal community belongs to the coastal areas, riverbanks, or the Sadi or Satapuda/Vidyanchal mountain ranges. Diversity is evident among the tribals of South Gujarat, who are economically more prosperous than those of North

Gujarat, and their folk culture includes "Kola, Padhar, Kotwaliya, Sidi, Kacholi".

According to the 11th census, India has 46 tribal communities, of which Gujarat has more than the national average. The tribal community accounts for 14.75 per cent of the total population. Gujarat has the largest tribal area, Dang, in 94.5%. While the largest population is in Dahod district, the least tribal community is settled in Bhavnagar district (about 0.3%). In India, Mizoram has the highest percentage of tribals (about 94%), while the largest tribal region by population is in Uttar Pradesh.

Tribal life in Gujarat reveals two distinct patterns. Purely primitive age, which lives in the mountain region and secondly, acculturated communities, those who live in the plain region. The important tribes present today are Bhil, Charan, Dhanka, Dhodia, Dubla, Bharwad, Gamti, Kali, Kolcha, Parashi, Rabari, Siddi, Vasava, Vagari, and Wari. The State of Gujarat comprises 43 talukas across 14 Scheduled Tribe-dominant districts. These Talukas comprise a population of 86 lakh S.T. individuals. To ensure a better value of life for the tribal population, the Constitution of India has advocated the policy of positive discrimination and affirmative action.

Tribe Population in Gujarat

Population refers to a group of tribal people who share a predefined criterion, such as location, race, ethnicity, nationality, or religion. Demography is a social science that entails the statistical study of populations.

The population of Gujarat in **the 2011 Census of India** was 60,439,692. Of this, **8,917,174** tribal peoples belong to one of the Scheduled Tribes (STs), constituting **14.75** per cent of the state's total population. According to the 2021 census, the Gujarat population is 72,736,247, compared to 60,439,692 in the **2011 census**. The population growth rate in Gujarat increased to 5.74 per cent from 2011. The total number of males and females in Gujarat is **37,895,584** and **34,840,662**. Gujarat comprises **33** districts, further divided into talukas, regions and districts. **As of 2021**, Gujarat's population is **72,736,247**. The same figures were recorded as **71,521,926** and **70,208,143 in 2020 and 2019**. The state adds more than 1.2 million tribal people to its population annually.

Tribe Population in Panchmahal District

The total PanchMahal district population in rural areas is **2,055,949**, of which males and females **1,053,376** and **1,002,573**, respectively. In rural areas of PanchMahal district, the sex ratio is **952 females per 1000 males**. The total population of Panchmahal is **23,907,76**, of which males and females were **12,269,61** and female **98 0340**; the total tribe population of Panchmahal is **11,95388 (the year 2011)**. Panchmahal has 7 talukas: Ghoghamba, Godhra, Halol, Jambughoda, Kadana, Kalol, Khanpur, Lunawada, Morwa (Hadaf), Santrampur, Shehera, according to the 2011 census. Mainly, tribal groups live in the eastern belt of Gujarat, from Banaskantha to Umargam in Valsad. There are 25 tribal groups in Gujarat. Among the

tribals of Gujarat, they are mainly found in the Banaskantha, Sabarkantha, and Aravalli districts of North Gujarat, and in Dahod, Panchmahal, Mahisagar, Vadodara, and Chhota Udaipur in South Gujarat.

The Impact of Education on Tribes

Education is a weapon for changing a human or society. Through Education, we have seen daily that tribal culture, Education, and lifestyle are changing. Therefore, Education is essential for the overall development of tribal society. Realising its importance, every government have invested in this sector to improve the quality of education and achieve the optimal goal in tribal society. "Tribal society

understands that education is a wealth, necessary to accomplish the idea of Peace, Liberty and Social Justice, to face the challenges. This is stated in the UNESCO report "Learning the treasure within" of the International Commission on Education for the 21st Century, which describes Education as an indispensable ideal. The Commission supports the view that Education has to play a very significant role in the development of an individual and society. Of course, the Commission believes that Education is not a panacea for all problems. Nevertheless, Education is powerful enough to cultivate the capacity for achieving sustainable development in a tribal society.

The literacy rate among the general population and tribal population in Gujarat, decade-wise (according to the census 2011)

Decade	Total Population of the State (in lakhs)	Total Population of STs (in lakhs)	Percentage concerning the tribal people of the State	Literacy among the General Population %	Literacy among STs %	Difference rate between the two %
1961	206.33	27.54	13.35	30.45	11.69	18.76
1971	266.97	37.34	13.99	35.79	14.12	21.67
1981	340.86	48.49	14.23	43.70	21.10	22.54
1991	413.10	61.62	14.92	51.15	29.67	21.48
2001	506.71	74.81	14.76	69.4	47.74	21.40
2011	604.39	89.17	14.75	72.98	61.1	11.98

The literacy rate among the general population and tribal population in Panchmahal District (according to census 2011)

Decade	Total Population of the State (in lakhs)	Total Population of STs (in lakhs)	Percentage concerning the tribal people of the State	Literacy among the General Population %	Literacy among STs %	The difference in rate between the two %
1961	8.88	4.22	47.52	20.3	4.73	15.57
1971	11.06	5.41	48.91	28.4	7.82	20.58
1981	13.75	6.73	48.94	35.7	13.40	22.3
1991	16.82	8.24	48.98	45.8	23.07	22.13
2001	20.25	9.45	46.66	60.92	44.13	16.79
2011	23.90	11.95	50	70.99	59.09	11.9

From these data, we can see that year by year, the educational data and the percentage are increasing in Gujarat. We found that the Panchmahal district's educational system has been improving from the past to the present. This is because the tribal population has been awarded for Education. The state government has many plans for tribal development. Education is much more than most tribal people understand; it goes beyond getting various certificates or reading a book. Education is a process that aims to provide instruction to instil good morals, a positive attitude towards life, ethical behaviour, and a sense of responsibility to help others. Education is the essential aspect of tribal people's development as it provides a revenue to help tribal people to grow economically and broaden their understanding of cultural and social practices in the tribal community of Panchmahal district.

Educational Development

It is also true that all the communities of the Panchmahal tribes live their lives in some sense scientifically. The tribes' necessities and expectations are: the more their scientific knowledge is, the more limited it is. Education has the greatest value. All those activities that are good, useful and valuable from an educational point of view are considered educational values. Education aims to modify the nature of the tribal student, not merely to provide a certain amount of knowledge.

According to J. Ruskin, "Education does not mean teaching tribal people to know that they do not know. It means teaching them to behave as they do not behave". Thus, the ultimate goal of Education is to achieve the good life.

Impact of Education on the Educational Development of Tribal Students

Educational Development In Tribal Student	Sub Category of Educational Development	Obtain Marks	Total Marks	Percentage%
Educational Development In Tribal Student	Astrology	1025	1200	85.41%
Educational Development In Tribal Student		759	1200	63.25%
Educational Development In Tribal Student	Scientific knowledge	999	1200	83.25%
Educational Development In Tribal Student	Awareness of Education	1019	1200	84.91%
Educational Development In Tribal Student		853	1200	71.08%
Total Educational Development	Total Educational Development	5560	7200	77.22%

The Development of Tribal Traditional Students through Education in the Panchmahal District

Within the Panchmahal district, the urban area is well off. However, the community villages are undergoing significant changes in infrastructure and basic amenities.

Through education, some values have been updated, such as continuity and giving up, among the tribal people of Panchmahal District.

Impact of Education upon Value in Tribal Students of Panchmahal District

Value Sustain in present time	Partially Lost Value	Totally Lost Value
Culture	Facing challenge	Covering with clay
Lifestyle	Toughness	Making clay pipes for making stoves/
Truth - faith	Dedication	Covering a house with tarpaulin
Self-esteem	Brotherhood	Making tarpaulin from satra leaves
Systematization-Utilization of resources	Family Unity	Zamindari system
Family Discipline	Traditional wedding ceremonies	Low caste/High function of society to do

Superstition	Long duration of marriage rituals	unity of society
Nutrition	Paying tribute by gathering in groups.	Lack of transportation
Simplicityz	Playing the role of participation in the grief of relatives	Lack of education / intelligence Lack
Honesty	Giving traditional dowry system.	To get water by digging wells
Respect for fathers	Using only hand tools, bamboo or to use the eye.	To prepare the materials necessary for building a house by oneself.
Social Service	social tradition / Giving financial support (contribution)	Tools from agriculture – carpentry work and self use Plow – wood, making hands
Religious Beliefs	It is equal to God to treat a guest with respect.	Following oneself
Humanity	Be respectful towards strangers.	Cooperation in agriculture
Art passed from generation to generation	social service.	Using forest plant seeds
Courage to face challenges.	Superior-inferior discrimination	Level of illiteracy in the community

Impact of Education on tribal students in various areas

Sequence Number	Category	Total obtain mark	Total mark	Percentage
1	Economic Development	1766	2400	73.58%
2	Social Development	8811	10800	81.58%
3	Traditional Development	19210	32400	59.29%
4	Psychological Development	3195	17600	18.15%
5	Moral Development	5928	43200	13.72%
6	Personal Development	18354	85600	21.44158879%
7	Educational Development	5560	7200	77.22%

The table shows that overall Economic development in the tribal student is 78.58%, the social development in the tribal student is 81.58%, The traditional development in the tribal student is 59.29%, The psychological Development is 18.15%, The Moral Development in a tribal student is 13.72%, The Personal Development in Tribal student is 21.44%, The Educational Development in Tribal student is 77.22%.

Conclusion

"Education is a process of transmitting knowledge, attitude and skills to the tribal people who require it".

"Education is the engine of economic growth and social change. It motivates progress and revolution the ideas necessary for the country's progress. It teaches honesty, inspires patriotism, enhances social prestige and promotes economic Development. When tribal people are educated, we get teachers, professionals and executives and, more importantly, citizens who are aware, sensitive and responsible. It makes tribal people place social good above tribal people gains. Not only this, it transforms a human being into a wholesale whole, a noble soul and an asset to the universe" (Kalam, 2004).

The role of Education in the Development of a nation has been considered so vital that no nation can afford to ignore it, be it a developing or a developed country.

That is why there is a social demand for Education. This social demand is the pressure of the masses for access to Education. This pressure is expressed through national and International declarations that cover the right of everyone to Education. This social demand is closely associated with measures such as compulsory schooling, the creation of institutions, free Education, an open learning system, equal educational opportunity for the citizens, etc.

The central and state governments are extending various facilities to promote tribal Education. The main reason behind these efforts is that most developed and developing nations have perceived a close link between Education and Development. This is strongly supported by many economists worldwide.

It, however, remains to be closely examined as the impact of Education on the Development of tribes in Gujarat and whether Education affects the tribal people's social, economic and political development in Gujarat.

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